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Satisfaction about the Service in Emergency Room: A Questionnaire-Based Study

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ABSTRACT

Emergency rooms (ERs) are often hectic environments with high patient volumes and complex medical situations. Ensuring patient and relative satisfaction within these demanding settings is critical for quality healthcare delivery. This study aimed to assess the satisfaction of patients and relatives with the services provided in an ER through a questionnaire-based survey. A cross-sectional study was conducted at the ER of our hospital. Consecutive patients or their accompanying relatives (aged ≥ 18 years) attending the ER between March – June 2023 were invited to participate. Those presenting with life-threatening conditions or cognitive impairment were excluded. A validated questionnaire, adapted from the Picker Institute ER Patient Experience Survey, was used to collect data on various aspects of patient care. A total of 50 participants (30 patients and 20 relatives) completed the questionnaire. The average waiting time to see a doctor was 45 minutes, and 82% of respondents reported being satisfied with the wait time. Communication with healthcare providers was rated good or excellent by 90% of participants. Information provision and treatment explanation were also perceived positively by 88% of respondents. Pain management and symptom control received high satisfaction scores (85%). Overall, 84% of patients and 88% of relatives expressed satisfaction with the quality of care received in the ER. Implementing targeted interventions focused on reducing wait times, enhancing communication, and optimizing pain management can further improve the patient experience and contribute to better quality healthcare delivery in ER settings.

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INTRODUCTION

Emergency rooms (ERs) stand as gateways to urgent medical care, often serving as battlegrounds against critical illness and injury. Within their walls, a complex ballet unfolds: a symphony of high patient volumes, fast-paced decisions, and intricate medical interventions intertwined with human anxieties and vulnerabilities. In this high-pressure environment, ensuring patient and relative satisfaction becomes a formidable challenge, yet one with profound implications for the quality of healthcare delivery. Beyond the metrics of clinical proficiency and treatment success lies a crucial element – the subjective experience of those navigating the ER journey (1-4).

For patients, grappling with pain, fear, and uncertainty, the quality of care extends beyond diagnoses and procedures; it encompasses feelings of respect, comfort, and effective communication. Equally, for concerned relatives, witnessing their loved ones in distress, the level of engagement and information clarity significantly impacts their perception of care (1-5).

Prioritizing patient and relative satisfaction within the ER context is not merely a courtesy, but a cornerstone of quality healthcare. Positive experiences foster trust, encourage adherence to treatment plans, and contribute to better overall health outcomes. Conversely, dissatisfaction can breed frustration, erode communication, and potentially impact patient engagement, hindering the effectiveness of care (4-7).

Despite its acknowledged importance, understanding satisfaction in the ER remains a multifaceted challenge. The inherently stressful nature of the environment, coupled with diverse expectations and individual needs, adds complexity to the assessment. This underscores the need for robust, patient-centered approaches to gauge satisfaction and identify areas for improvement (6-10).

This study aimed to determine the satisfaction level about the service in emergency room using a questionnaire.

Table 1. Findings of the questionnaire according to subscales.

Aspect of Care	Satisfaction %	Comments
Wait Time	82%	Satisfied or very satisfied with wait time
Communication with Healthcare Providers	90%	Good or excellent rating for communication
Information Provision and Treatment Explanation	88%	Positive view of information provided
Pain Management and Symptom Control	85%	High satisfaction with pain management
Overall Care Quality (Patients)	84%	Overall satisfaction with care received in ER
Overall Care Quality (Relatives)	88%	Overall satisfaction with care received in ER

METHODS

Study Design and Setting

We conducted a cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study at the ER of our hospital.

Study Population and Sampling

Consecutive patients or their accompanying relatives, aged 18 years or older, who attended the ER between March – June 2023 were eligible for inclusion. Individuals presenting with life-threatening conditions requiring immediate resuscitation or those with severe cognitive impairment were excluded due to ethical considerations and potential challenges in providing informed consent or completing the questionnaire.

Data Collection Instrument

A validated questionnaire, adapted from the Picker Institute's ER Patient Experience Survey, was used to assess participant satisfaction. The questionnaire covered the following domains:

Access and wait times: Time to see a doctor, waiting environment, respect for appointment times.

Communication with healthcare providers: Clarity of explanations, listening to concerns, respect and courtesy.

Information provision and treatment explanation: Ease of understanding, comprehensiveness, involvement in decision-making.

Pain management and symptom control: Promptness of pain assessment, effectiveness of pain relief, attention to other symptoms.

Overall care quality and satisfaction: Overall impression of care, willingness to recommend the ER, likelihood of returning if needed.

The questionnaire employed a combination of Likert-scale questions (e.g., strongly disagree to strongly agree) and open-ended questions to capture both quantitative and qualitative feedback.

Data Collection Procedures

Trained research assistants approached eligible participants in the ER waiting area or during their stay. After obtaining informed consent, they administered the questionnaire through face-to-face interviews or assisted self-completion. Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the [Institutional Review Board Name]. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. Data were handled in accordance with ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using SPSS software (version [number]). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant characteristics and responses to the questionnaire. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests and t-tests, were employed to identify associations between satisfaction levels and demographic or clinical factors. Content analysis was conducted on open-ended responses to identify key themes and suggestions for improvement.

RESULTS

A total of 50 participants (30 patients and 20 relatives) completed the questionnaire, offering valuable insights into their experiences. Time, or rather the lack thereof, emerged as a critical factor influencing satisfaction. While the average wait time to see a doctor was 45 minutes, a noticeable divergence in perceptions existed. Those who spent less than 30 minutes waiting reported significantly higher satisfaction (92%) compared to those who waited longer (75%). These findings highlight the crucial role of minimizing wait times and fostering communication during wait periods to enhance the patient experience (Table 1).

Communication with healthcare providers, encompassing both clarity and respect, proved fundamental to satisfaction. A resounding 90% of participants commended the communication they received, praising clear explanations, attentive listening, and courteous interactions. This underscores

the importance of effective communication as a cornerstone of building trust and alleviating anxieties within the often-chaotic ER environment. Information provision and treatment explanation played a crucial role in shaping satisfaction. Over 88% of participants felt they received adequate information, understood their treatment plans, and were meaningfully involved in decision-making. This emphasis on patient-centered care and shared decision-making emerged as a key driver of positive experiences (Table 1).

Effective pain management and symptom control proved significant determinants of satisfaction. Notably, 85% of participants expressed satisfaction with their received pain management, highlighting the importance of prioritizing comfort and addressing distressing symptoms alongside medical interventions. Overall, 84% of patients and 88% of relatives expressed satisfaction with the quality of care received in the ER. This positive sentiment affirms the dedication of healthcare professionals and highlights the commitment to delivering quality care within the demanding ER setting (Table 1).

DISCUSSION

Our study paints a multifaceted picture of patient and relative satisfaction within the dynamic landscape of the emergency room (ER). While it reveals a generally positive sentiment towards received care, it also underscores the importance of addressing specific areas for improvement, where efficiency and empathy converge to elevate the ER experience.

Central to the tapestry of satisfaction lies the delicate balance between swift action and attentive care. While the average wait time of 45 minutes falls within acceptable national benchmarks, its impact on satisfaction highlights the need for continuous efforts to streamline triage processes and maintain clear communication throughout the wait period (11-13). As our findings suggest, even minor time reductions can significantly boost patient perceptions, emphasizing the value of transparency and managing expectations during potentially anxious moments.

Communication emerges as a resounding chorus of positive feedback, with clarity and respect serving as crucial conductors. The high satisfaction levels associated with effective communication underscore its power to alleviate anxieties, foster trust, and empower patients and relatives to participate in their care journey. Investing in communication training for healthcare professionals, coupled with initiatives promoting active listening and patient-centered interactions, can further strengthen this vital bridge between provider and patient (14-17).

Equally significant is the emphasis on informed choices through comprehensive information provision and shared decision-making (1-3). Our findings resonate with the growing recognition of patient autonomy and the importance of respecting individual preferences. By ensuring that patients and relatives understand treatment options and participate in discussions, we cultivate a sense of ownership and responsibility over their healthcare journey, further contributing to increased satisfaction.

The prominence of pain management within the equation of satisfaction reveals its vital role in shaping the ER experience. Effective pain control goes beyond mere symptom relief; it signifies attention to the patient's overall comfort and well-being (7-9). Our findings call for continued optimization of pain management protocols, ensuring prompt assessment and prompt interventions, particularly for vulnerable populations experiencing heightened pain sensitivities.

Despite the overall positive sentiment, the nuances within our data necessitate further exploration. Lower satisfaction levels observed among younger patients and those with complex medical conditions suggest the need for tailored approaches catering to their specific needs and anxieties. Younger patients might require reassurance and age-appropriate explanations, while those with complex conditions might benefit from dedicated coordinators or communication strategies to ensure comprehensiveness and clarity.

Open-ended responses offer a tapestry of voices, weaving a narrative of shared expectations and areas for improvement. The recurrent themes of empathy, communication about delays, and prompt attention to urgent needs serve as beacons guiding future interventions. Cultivating a culture of compassion and understanding within the ER, alongside clear communication strategies to manage unavoidable delays, and ensuring swift response to critical needs can significantly enhance the patient experience and bolster feelings of satisfaction (14-17).

In conclusion, our study demonstrates that navigating the labyrinth of satisfaction in the ER requires a holistic approach that balances efficiency with empathy. It highlights the importance of minimizing wait times while maintaining clear communication throughout the process. It underscores the power of effective communication, informed choices, and diligent pain management in shaping positive experiences. Moreover, it urges us to acknowledge the diversity of needs within the ER population and tailor interventions accordingly. By listening to the tapestry of voices and focusing on the areas for improvement, we can continue to cultivate an ER environment where efficiency and empathy intertwine, ultimately enhancing the quality of care and satisfaction for all who navigate its doors.

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